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2 **Abnormalities of the Cingulate Cortex in Myalgic**
3 **Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome**

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19 **Abstract**

20

21 Myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome (ME/CFS) is a chronic condition associated with a
22 high burden of physical disability and an elevated prevalence of cognitive symptoms. Patients show
23 abnormalities in several domains, including systemic and brain metabolism, and the immune system.
24 But the mechanism behind the disease is unknown and there is no cure. Patients with ME/CFS exhibit
25 significant changes in the cingulate cortex, including reduced glucose metabolism, altered resting-state
26 connectivity, increased activation during cognitive tasks, and increased glial activation, all reviewed in
27 this paper. We also show that our analysis of the local spectrum in the cingulate cortex of a patient with
28 ME/CFS confirms the increase of the CHO/CR ratio reported by a previous study. We discuss how a
29 pathology of the cingulate cortex is also confirmed indirectly by cognitive assessment in this patient
30 population. The mechanism behind these abnormalities remains unknown. In this paper, we show that
31 some of these abnormalities are consistent with what is seen in systemic inflammation. We also review
32 some evidence pointing to the hypothesis that they could be secondary to a pathology of the brainstem,
33 including the metabolic shift in the serotonergic neurons of the Raphe nuclei described by a recent
34 mathematical model of ME/CFS. Alternatively, we propose that the increased CHO/CR ratio in the
35 anterior cingulate cortex may also be a sign of abnormal plasma membrane composition, which is
36 suggested by metabolomic studies and by measures of the electrical properties of PBMCs and plasma,
37 in this patient population.

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44 **1 Introduction**

45

46 Myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome (ME/CFS) is a chronic debilitating disease affecting
47 up to 2.5 million people in the US. The illness often starts after an infectious episode and is characterized
48 by extreme fatigue, cognitive impairment, and orthostatic intolerance. The diagnosis is based on clinical
49 evaluation and requires a substantial reduction in activity level compared to pre-illness. Most of the
50 patients affected are unable to work or attend school full-time (1), (2). Worsening of symptoms after
51 exertion, referred to as post-exertional malaise (PEM), might have different presentations and patterns
52 among patients (3), but it is increasingly recognized as a pathognomonic symptom of ME/CFS (1).
53 Despite evidence of many kinds of abnormalities, such as altered systemic (4), (5), (6), and brain
54 metabolism (7), (8), (9), impaired aerobic performances (especially following exertion) (10), direct (11)
55 and indirect (12) proofs of a genetic basis, signs of systemic (13) as well as central inflammation (14),
56 (9), and evidence pointing towards autoimmune processes (15), (16), the etiopathophysiology of
57 ME/CFS is elusive and matter of debate (17). There is no current consensus and there are no FDA
58 approved treatments (1). Annual direct medical costs for patients with ME/CFS in the U.S. are three to
59 four times higher than for the general insured population and fifty per cent higher than for multiple
60 sclerosis or lupus (18). The annual cost to the economy from ME/CFS has been estimated to be \$ 17–
61 \$ 24 billion in the U.S. alone (19).

62 More than 95% of patients will never experience a sustained improvement of their condition, even
63 though several patterns of the illness are recorded, the most common being a fluctuating course with
64 symptoms changing in intensity, although always present (20), (2).

65 Postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome (POTS), a form of orthostatic intolerance that can be
66 objectively assessed with a set of hemodynamic measures, seems to be common among ME/CFS
67 patients, with a prevalence ranging from 13% to 81% across studies (2). A review of the literature has
68 reported a prevalence for POTS of about 27% in patients and 4.2% in healthy controls (1).

69 Granted that the diagnostic criteria admit the possibility of having a diagnosis of ME/CFS also in the
70 case of no cognitive complaints (21), (22), (1), a form of cognitive impairment is reported by the majority
71 of patients, with the two most prevalent complaints being problems remembering things and difficulties
72 expressing thoughts. Difficulty in paying attention is lamented by more than 60% of this patient
73 population (23), (2). Despite objective evidence of slowed reaction time in attention tasks that does not
74 correlate to depression or anxiety and that is associated to greater neural engagement of cortical and
75 subcortical areas (24), (25), (26), (27), (28), (29), there seems to be a lack of sensitivity in current
76 cognitive assessment in this patient population (30). Therefore, further studies and the development of
77 new tools are warranted. The cingulate cortex, particularly the middle cingulate cortex (MCC) and the
78 anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), is one of the cortical regions consistently reported as differentially
79 activated during attention tasks in ME/CFS. It has also shown abnormal metabolism (8), (31), (9) and
80 altered functional connectivity (32). As such, this region may not only hold clues about the mechanisms
81 behind cognitive dysfunction in ME/CFS but also offer a way to objectively measure it. In the review
82 about ME/CFS published by the Academy of Medicine in 2015, in the section on neurocognitive
83 manifestations, the Authors suggested that structural differences in ACC/MCC could be a biomarker of
84 conditions such as ME/CFS (1).

85

86 **2 Cingulate cortex**

87

88 **2.1 Anatomy and parcellation**

89

90 The cingulate cortex is the region of the medial surface of the cerebral cortex that wraps around the
91 corpus callosum. It is delimited rostrally and dorsally by the paracingulate and the cingulate sulci, while
92 the splenial sulcus is the posterior border. The callosal sulcus represents its ventral limit (Figure 1, A)
93 (33). The parcellation of the cingulate gyrus has been a matter of debate: many nomenclatures are

94 available, leading to some confusion. Following the limits of the Brodmann areas (BA) 24 and 32 (Figure
95 2, A), it was originally accepted to define anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) the most rostral two-thirds of
96 the cingulate cortex, further dividing this region between a rostral region (rACC) that extends in front of
97 and below the genu of the corpus callosum, and a dorsal one (dACC), that covers the middle third of
98 the cingulate cortex (34). But studies of cytoarchitecture and receptor binding, as well as functional
99 studies and connectivity mapping analyses have consistently shown that the so-called dACC can no
100 longer be considered part of the ACC (35). Accordingly, the first version of the automated anatomical
101 atlas (AAL), a brain labelling system widely used in neuroimaging research (36), introduces the label of
102 midcingulate cortex (MCC) for the area of the cingulate cortex whose MNI coordinates satisfy the
103 conditions: $z \geq 32$ and $-50 \leq y \leq 30$; while the ACC is the rostral region below the line $z = 32$ (Figure
104 1, B). What is left of the cingulate cortex is the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC). This parcellation has
105 been recently further refined (AAL3), with the subdivision of ACC in the supracallosal ACC ($y \leq 36$ and
106 $z \geq 3$), the pregenual (or perigenual) ACC ($y \geq 37$), and the subgenual ACC ($y \leq 36$ and $z < 3$) (37).
107 This subdivision is almost equivalent to the one proposed by Vogt (Figure 2, B) (35) for what concerns
108 the boundary between the ACC and the MCC, with the caveat that the ACC defined in AAL/AAL3 may
109 extend posteriorly into what is considered part of the MCC by Vogt. Moreover, in Vogt's definition, the
110 PCC houses the whole BA 23 (along with BA 29, 30, and 31), while in AAL and AAL3 most of BA 23 is
111 included in MCC. Another issue is that while AAL is normalized to the Montreal Neurologic Institute
112 (MNI) standard stereotactic space (38), Vogt's nomenclature is overlaid on the Talairach and Tournoux
113 space (39). Many current studies employ the AAL atlas for the interpretation of the results of fMRI data,
114 while others use the subdivision by Vogt, and some still maintain the label of dACC. In the present study,
115 we translated all the data into Vogt's subdivision. In order to do that, we interrogated the Brodmann Map
116 and the AAL3 atlas in MNI space, provided with MRIcron (40). We also used some custom codes for
117 coordinate conversion from MNI space into Talairach and Tournoux space, and for the inverse
118 transformation (see par. 3.5).

119

120 **2.2 Functions**

121

122 Twenty years ago, a meta-analysis of 64 fMRI scans and PET imaging studies showed that cognitive
123 tasks consistently activated MCC (particularly the dorsal anterior region) while deactivating ACC and
124 that, conversely, emotionally valenced tasks selectively activated ACC and deactivated MCC (41).
125 Today it is recognized that, while the MCC is linked to cognitive processing and reward-based decision
126 making, the ACC is devolved to processing emotions and regulating the endocrine and autonomic
127 response to them (42).

128

129 **ACC.** Functional MRI studies have shown that positive stimuli – such as pleasant touch or taste,
130 pleasant temperature applied to the hand, and pleasant odours – activate the most rostral part of ACC.
131 The same region is also activated by predicted positive outcomes of actions while unpleasant stimuli
132 activate a region just posterior to this one, the supracallosal ACC (43). Both these regions belong to the
133 pregenual ACC (pACC), according to Vogt’s nomenclature (Figure 2, B). The subgenual ACC (sACC)
134 is involved in the autonomic components of emotions, via its projections to hypothalamus and midbrain
135 (35).

136

137 **MCC.** It has been determined that the anterior MCC (aMCC) is selectively activated by cognitive tasks
138 in which the subject is exposed to conflicting simultaneous representations, such as the so-called Stroop
139 Colour-Word Test, a task in which the subject has to name the colour a word is written in, while the
140 meaning of the word actually indicates another colour. As an example, if the reader is asked to name
141 the colour in which the following word is written:

142

143

GREEN

144

145 their MCC will likely be activated as it senses a possible source of error and it recruits the dorsolateral
146 prefrontal cortex (DLPC) to solve the conflict (44).

147 In Table 1, we have collected the results, for the healthy controls, of the fMRI studies during cognitive
148 tasks discussed later in this paper. They give us the chance to review other functions of aMCC. In the
149 verbal n-back task, the examinee is presented with a series of capital letters and has to press a button
150 whenever a letter matches the one presented n trials previously, with n assuming values that span
151 from 1 (the lower level of difficulty) to 3. This is a test of working memory that has been found to activate
152 aMCC in healthy subjects (24), (29). More generally, it has been proven that some cells of the aMCC
153 display working memory properties, as reviewed here (45). In a study on 16 healthy females, it was
154 asked them to recognize whether letters, subjected to different degrees of rotation, were mirror images
155 of canonical letters or not; similarly, they were asked to report if the images of hands they were showed
156 represented right or left hands, regardless of their rotation. Error rate correlated with activation of L
157 aMCC and L pACC (28) and this points to another function of MCC: fMRI studies have reported aMCC
158 activation in response to error, as reviewed here (45).

159 The aMCC is also sensitive to novelties: in a PET study, the examinees were asked to name a verb
160 related to the object shown (for instance: pen \rightarrow write). Initially, this task activated aMCC, but as the
161 participants acquired familiarity with the list of objects, the activation faded; it increased again when
162 new objects were introduced (46).

163

164 **PCC.** It is activated by tasks involving biographical memory (consistently with its connections with the
165 hippocampal memory system) and by tasks of spatial navigation, as reviewed here (35). It has been
166 proposed by Rolls that PCC takes part in learning about the association between outputs and outcomes:
167 in this model, the information about action outcomes from ACC is integrated to information about actions
168 from PCC; this is elaborated within the cingulate cortex and an output from the MCC, which is connected
169 to neocortical motor areas, is produced (43).

170

171 **2.3 Cingulate cortex in ME/CFS**

172

173 Several abnormalities of the cingulate cortex have been documented in ME/CFS patients. Reduced
174 glucose metabolism in BA 24, 32 (ACC/MCC) and BA 23, 31 (PCC) was documented in a PET study
175 on 26 ME/CFS patients (8), (Table 8). Reduced resting-state connectivity between aMCC and the right
176 insula has been reported, as well as increased resting-state connectivity between aMCC and
177 hippocampus/PCC (32).

178 One consistent finding throughout the literature in this patient population is the abnormal activation of
179 the cingulate cortex during cognitive tasks (Table 2). An fMRI study showed a greater than normal BOLD
180 signal in L aMCC and R pMCC, during a modified version of the Paced Auditory Serial Attention Test
181 (mPASAT). In this task, examinees listen to a series of numbers and are required to mentally add the
182 first to the second, the second to the third, and so on, and to press a button whenever the result is equal
183 to ten. This group of patients presented a low PASAT score. When the same authors repeated the
184 experiment in patients with a normal PASAT score, they found a greater than normal BOLD signal in LR
185 aMCC and also in R pACC (27). In a subsequent fMRI study, patients showed a greater BOLD signal
186 from pMCC, bilaterally, during the second of three mPASAT sessions with incongruent stimuli. In this
187 task, patients were required to perform the mPASAT while looking at a screen where random changing
188 numbers were shown (25). This variant of the mPASAT presents incongruent stimuli, similarly to the
189 Stroop Colour-Word Test. In another fMRI study, patients with ME/CFS exhibited greater activation in
190 ACC, MCC, and PCC, bilaterally, compared to controls, during the Stroop Colour-Word Test (26). A
191 greater BOLD signal in L pACC in patients vs controls was detected in a study in which patients were
192 required to perform a verbal version of the n-back task, but only during the less difficult task (1-back).
193 Activation in this same region was negatively correlated with task load (24). Recently, a study using
194 verbal n-back task showed no differences between patients and controls: similar activation of RL MCC
195 was detected in both groups. But in this study, only 2-back was performed (and 0-back as a comparison),
196 so the results are coherent with the previous ones (29).

197 In a study in which patients and controls were asked to detect whether a letter was a specular reflection
198 of the canonical letter and to distinguish left and right hands, regardless of their rotation, the activation
199 of L aMCC/pACC in concomitance with errors was greater in controls than in patients (28). This study
200 suggests that the error detection activity of aMCC (par. 2.2) is deficient among ME/CFS patients.

201 In ME/CFS, cerebral blood flow in ACC and MCC has been investigated in at least three studies, all of
202 them using arterial spin labelling (ASL) – a method in which arterial blood water entering the brain is
203 magnetically labelled and used as a tracer (47) – and no differences with healthy subjects have been
204 documented (48), (49), (9), (Table 7).

205 In a recent study employing whole-brain magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS), the main difference
206 between ME/CFS patients and healthy controls was an increase in the choline on creatine ratio
207 (CHO/CR) in the ACC (as defined by the AAL labelling system, thus including part of aMCC), mainly in
208 the left hemisphere (9). If we interpret this result as a sign of neuroinflammation (see par. 3.2), it is in
209 agreement with a previous PET study that showed increased $^{11}\text{C}(\text{R})\text{PK11195}$ binding in a region of
210 interest (ROI) corresponding to the whole cingulate cortex (14) (Table 3). This radiotracer is known to
211 bind the translocator protein (TSPO), an 18kDa protein expressed in the mitochondrial membrane of
212 neurons, microglia, and astrocytes that undergoes a substantial increase in expression in microglia and
213 astrocytes, during inflammatory processes and other kinds of CNS challenges (50). A previous MRS
214 study on 12 patients who met the Oxford criteria showed only a slight and non-statistically significant
215 increase in CHO in voxels placed in pACC, compared to 25 healthy controls (31).

216

217 **2.4 Cingulate cortex and fatigue**

218

219 Some studies across different conditions suggest a link between abnormalities in the cingulate cortex
220 and fatigue. In ME/CFS, the aforementioned fMRI study that employed the mPASAT with concomitant
221 incongruent stimuli reported an association between the BOLD signal in L MCC/PCC and both mental
222 fatigue after task, and baseline fatigue, in the total sample. Mental fatigue was assessed using the Visual

223 Analog Scale (VAS), while baseline fatigue was measured according to the Profile of Moods States
224 (POMS) (25).

225 In iatrogenic systemic inflammation induced by typhoid vaccination, 16 healthy males showed a positive
226 correlation between the BOLD signal in L pACC and L aMCC, and fatigue, during the Stroop Colour-
227 Word Test (51), (Table 2).

228 A recent whole-brain MRS study on 18 women with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) found that the CHO/CR
229 ratio in R MCC (and in other regions) correlates with fatigue (VAS) (52). In fibromyalgia (FM), a PET
230 study employing the TSPO radioligand [¹¹C]PBR28, found that the uptake in aMCC/pMCC correlates
231 with fatigue, as measured with the American College of Rheumatology self-report survey for the
232 assessment of FM (ACR) (53), (Table 3).

233

234 **2.5 Cognitive dysfunction in ME/CFS**

235

236 A recent survey on 150 patients fitting Fukuda criteria reported a high prevalence of self-reported
237 cognitive complaints, the most prevalent being problems remembering things (68%) and difficulties
238 expressing thoughts (68%), followed by difficulty in paying attention (64%) (2), in agreement with a
239 previous study on 236 cases, selected according to Fukuda or Canadian Consensus Criteria (CCC)
240 (23). In 2016, a review on objective measures of cognitive functioning among this patient population has
241 concluded that studies consistently report a slowed reaction time in tasks requiring button-press
242 responses to simple visual stimuli, which cannot be attributed solely to a slowing of motor function.
243 Reaction time in more complex tasks, such as the Stroop Colour-Word Test and its variants, was longer
244 compared with controls, too. Despite that, accuracy in these tasks was not affected by the disease,
245 according to the review (30).

246 The studies collected in Table 2 show that patients had a normal performance on the verbal n-back task
247 (24), and in one of the two studies employing the mPASAT without incongruent stimuli (27). But in the
248 more challenging mPASAT with associated incongruent stimuli, they were slower and less accurate

249 than normal (25). Moreover, a higher than normal number of missed responses was registered among
250 patients during the visual task with simultaneous rotations and reflections of images (28). Patients were
251 also slower than healthy controls in the Stroop Colour-Word Test (26). Recently, a slower processing
252 speed than healthy controls in the Stroop Colour-Word Test has been confirmed in another paper (54).
253 Several biological markers have shown a correlation with cognitive symptoms in ME/CFS. In the
254 Japanese PET study with specific TSPO radioligand, binding in the midbrain, amygdala, and the L
255 thalamic intralaminar nucleus correlates with self-reported cognitive impairment (14). In one of the
256 aforementioned studies, the performances on the Stroop Task (colour-naming trial) positively correlates
257 with heart rate variability (HRV) (54). Similarly, a previous study found a positive correlation between
258 HRV and performances across several cognitive tasks (55). HRV is considered a surrogate index of
259 resting cardiac vagal outflow and has been found to positively correlate to the cortical thickness of aMCC
260 (56), therefore the positive association between cognitive performances and HRV might be further proof
261 of abnormality in MCC among patients with ME/CFS. As mentioned in par. 2.3, patients with ME/CFS
262 display greater than normal activation of MCC bilaterally during cognitive tasks, and also of ACC.
263 Moreover, in the same studies, patients exhibit a greater than normal recruitments of several other
264 cortical and subcortical structures, while performing cognitive tasks. For instance, during the Stroop
265 Colour-Word Task, patients with ME/CFS showed wider activated areas not only in the cingulate cortex,
266 but also in the frontal, temporal, parietal, and occipital lobes, as well as in amygdala, hippocampus,
267 thalamus, and basal ganglia (26). These findings suggest that in ME/CFS a greater neuronal
268 engagement of both cortical and subcortical structures is required to maintain a normal accuracy in
269 cognitive tasks.

270

271 **3 A case study**

272

273 **3.1 Clinical story**

274

275 The patient was attending high school when he suffered from an episode of pneumonia with respiratory
276 complications and a high fever that lasted 5 months and required three hospitalizations. The triggering
277 pathogen was not identified. He was 16 years old at the time (2013). His scholastic performance and
278 his physical functioning significantly declined, but he was able to graduate from high school. His
279 condition worsened afterwards: the patient became housebound and all physical and cognitive activities
280 had to be stopped. In 2018, the patient was diagnosed with ME/CFS, after exploring other possible
281 etiologies. The same year, a positive tilt table test led to the diagnosis of postural tachycardia syndrome
282 (POTS).

283 Physical and cognitive abilities are reduced after exertion and the patient is especially vulnerable to
284 exertion deriving from cognitive tasks. The disease course is of slow deterioration and he is now
285 completely unable to care for his basic needs. The symptoms and clinical picture are consistent with the
286 2015 IOM ME/CFS criteria (1).

287 The clinical picture is dominated by profound cognitive dysfunction, extreme fatigue and sleep
288 dysfunction (circadian rhythm inversion, non-24-hour sleep-wake disorder and unrefreshing sleep).
289 Gastrointestinal symptoms (gastroparesis, gastroesophageal reflux, and occasional diarrhoea) are
290 present.

291

292 **3.2 Magnetic resonance with spectroscopy**

293

294 Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is one of the most important noninvasive imaging techniques in
295 medicine. Its physical basis is the so-called Larmor's precession, the precession of the magnetic
296 moment of an object about an external magnetic field B . It is known that the magnetic moment precesses
297 with an angular frequency given by the Larmor's equation: $\omega = \gamma B$, where γ is a property of the object,
298 called gyromagnetic ratio. Since nuclei and particles with a spin number (I) larger than zero have an
299 associated magnetic moment $\mu = \gamma I$, Larmor's equation applies to them too. When an electromagnetic
300 radiofrequency pulse (RF pulse) is applied with a frequency equal to the precession angular frequency

301 of the particle (condition of resonance), the particle absorbs energy from the RF pulse and then releases
302 the same energy as photons with a frequency equal to ω . If the RF pulse has three spatial gradients, it
303 is possible to localize the source of this emission in a cartesian system of coordinates (57). This is the
304 basis of MRI. Since hydrogen is the most abundant element in the human body and its nucleus (whose
305 spin is $\frac{1}{2}$) has the largest magnetic moment among all stable nuclei, most of the MRI applications are
306 based on resonance of protons.

307 We have omitted to mention that the actual magnetic field a proton is immersed in depends on its
308 chemical environment, i.e. on the molecules that contain the hydrogen that proton belongs to. In order
309 to take this effect (called chemical shift) into account, we must use the following expression of the
310 Lamour's equation:

311

312 Eq. 1 $\omega = \gamma B(1 - \sigma)$

313

314 where σ is the shielding effect characteristic of each molecule. If we know the value of σ for a metabolite,
315 the use of an RF pulse with spatial gradients will allow us not only to localize the source of the resonance
316 emission, but also the concentration of that given metabolite in that region of the sample. This is the
317 basis of magnetic resonance with spectroscopy (MRS) (58). In MRS, the amplitude of the signal from a
318 voxel of the sample is plotted against the chemical shift of the metabolite, expressed in ppm (59). In
319 Figure 3, C there is an example of such a diagram (called local spectrum) for a voxel with a volume of
320 $10 \times 10 \times 10$ mm, placed in the cingulate cortex.

321

322 **N-acetyl aspartate (NAA)**. It has the highest peak, in normal brains. The corresponding frequency is
323 2.20 ppm. It is a marker of neuronal and axonal viability and density. Decreased NAA is thus a sign of
324 neuronal loss and degeneration (59).

325

326 **Creatine (CR).** Its peak at 3.02 ppm is a combination of creatine and phosphocreatine. It is a marker of
327 energetic metabolism and is relatively stable throughout the brain and among different individuals. For
328 this reason, metabolites are often normalized to creatine, allowing for comparisons across studies (59).
329 An elevation of CR has been consistently found in neuroinflammation (60).

330

331 **Choline (CHO).** The peak for CHO is at 3.22 ppm and it measures a combination of free choline and
332 water-soluble myelin and cell membrane components containing choline (as phosphocholine and
333 glycerophosphocholine) (59). An increase in CHO has been described in normal-appearing brain
334 parenchyma of subjects with infectious diseases involving the brain, like neuroborreliosis (61), hepatitis
335 C infection (62), HIV (63), and Toxoplasmosis (64). This and other evidence suggests that an elevated
336 level of CHO is present in neuroinflammation (60). There is also evidence that suggests a reduction of
337 CHO in M1 type microglia activation: an ex vivo MRS study on rats treated with escalating dosages of
338 lipopolysaccharide (LPS) showed decreased CHO in the hypothalamus, but not in thalamus, frontal
339 cortex and striatum (65); an in vivo study in mice treated with a single dose of LPS, reported on
340 decreased CHO in the hippocampus and the in upper part of the thalamus (66); LPS is known to polarize
341 microglia to an M1 phenotype (67).

342

343 **Myoinositol (MI).** It is a carbocyclic sugar assigned at 3.56 ppm. It is considered as a putative glial
344 marker since it is primarily present in glial cells (59). A review of MRS studies on multiple sclerosis (MS)
345 and neuroviral infections including HIV and hepatitis C (HCV) suggests that neuroinflammation is
346 associated with elevated levels of MI (60).

347

348 **3.3 Anatomical image acquisition**

349

350 Data were collected at the Pisa Research Area of the National Research Council (Italy), using a 3.0 T
351 MRI scanner. A spoiled gradient recalled acquisition in the steady-state (SPGR) sequence was acquired

352 for anatomical reference and brain labelling, using the following parameters: repetition time (TR) = 10.67
353 ms; echo time (TE) = 4.86 ms; flip angle = 16°; 166 sagittal slices; voxel size = 1 mm isotropic; dimension
354 = 256 x 256 x 166 mm.

355

356 **3.4 Spectroscopy**

357

358 Localized spectra were acquired the same day in the same session, using a Point RE-solved
359 Spectroscopy (PRESS) sequence with the following parameters: repetition time (TR) = 2.0 s; echo time
360 (TE) = 35 ms; flip angle = 90°. Four voxels were placed manually in the pregenual ACC (10x10x10 mm),
361 right hippocampus/amygdala (16x18x12 mm), pons (16x16x16 mm), and right centrum semiovale
362 (10x10x10). A control group of healthy subjects was available for the localized spectra in these regions,
363 collected with the same parameters. Metabolites were expressed as ratios of CR (Table 4).

364

365 **3.5 Processing protocol for the anatomical image**

366

367 The following steps of the analysis were performed using the Statistical Parametric Mapping 12 (SPM12)
368 standalone package. The origin of the coordinates for the anatomical image was manually placed on
369 the anterior commissure. We then co-registered the anatomical image (source image) with the Colin-27
370 atlas (reference image) (68), a high-resolution brain template constructed by acquiring twenty-seven
371 T1-weighted brain images of the same subject. A linear spatial transformation was applied along with
372 reslicing. The transformation of the old coordinates (x, y, z) into the new ones (x', y', z') is of the type:

373

$$374 \text{ Eq. 2 } \begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} m_{11} & m_{12} & m_{13} \\ m_{21} & m_{22} & m_{23} \\ m_{31} & m_{32} & m_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} m_{14} \\ m_{24} \\ m_{34} \end{bmatrix}$$

375

376 and it produces a rigid roto-translation plus scaling and shearing (69). The higher degree of interpolation
377 was used for reslicing.

378 We have used the transformation in Eq. 2 to find the MNI coordinates of the centres of each of the
379 voxels placed for the local spectra acquisition. We have also converted these points into the Talairach
380 and Tournoux space; to do that, we have adapted to Octave (70) the MATLAB function *mni2tal* (and its
381 inversion) which implements the so-called Brett transform (71), a tool commonly used for this conversion
382 (72). We have also coded in Octave the *icbm2tal* transform (and its inversion), considered to be more
383 accurate than the Brett transform (73). The labelling for the cingulate cortex follows the one proposed
384 by Vogt (Figure 2, B). For the labelling of the other regions, we have overlaid the AAL3 atlas (37) on the
385 anatomical image registered in MNI space, by using the latest version of MRIcron software (Table 4),
386 (Table 5).

387

388 **3.6 Statistical analysis**

389

390 The laboratory provided mean values and standard deviations of the ratios NAA/CR, CHO/CR, and
391 MI/CR of a healthy control group, for each of the four localized spectra. The actual distributions of these
392 ratios were not available. We used the one-sided Chebyshev's inequality (Eq. 3) to decide whether a
393 ratio was significantly altered (increased or reduced) in our patient, in comparison with the control group
394 [27]. This analysis was performed by a custom script in Octave.

395

396 Eq. 3
$$P(|x - \mu_x| \geq \eta_x) \leq \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\eta_x^2}$$

397

398 In Eq. 3, x is the ratio between a metabolite and CR, in a healthy subject, μ_x is its mean in the healthy
399 control group, and σ_x is its standard deviation in the control group. The value for that specific ratio in our

400 patient is given by $\mu_x + \eta_x$, if it is above the mean; by $\mu_x - \eta_x$ if it is equal or lower than μ_x . So, for
401 instance, for NAA/CR in aMCC, Eq. 3 is written as follows:

402

403 Eq. 4 $P(|x - 1.55| \geq |1.37 - 1.55| = 0.18) \leq \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\eta_x^2} = 0.3086$

404

405 which means that the probability that the NAA/CR ratio in aMCC, in a healthy subject, is greater than
406 the ratio registered in our patient, is below 0.3086. We set as statistically significant a value ≤ 0.05 , so
407 the NAA/CR ratio measured in our patient would be considered normal, according to our method.

408

409 **3.7 Other measures**

410

411 Cytokines in serum (IL-1 α , IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-17, TNF α , TGF β 1, and IFN γ) were
412 measured during the 5 weeks before the MRI with spectroscopy and 3 months after (Table 6). One
413 month before the MRI, the patient was also subjected to a cognitive evaluation.

414

415 **3.8 Results**

416

417 The only statistically significant alteration in our patient is the CHO/CR ratio for the voxel placed in the
418 cingulate cortex (Table 4). This ratio is 5.67 standard deviations above the mean of the control group.
419 According to the one-sided Chebyshev's inequality, this means that the probability for a healthy
420 individual to have a value greater or equal to this is at most 0.03. In other words, the percentage of
421 healthy individuals with a CHO/CR ratio, in this region, greater or equal to the one found in our patient
422 is at most 3.0 %. The localization of the centre of this voxel, according to the AAL3 labelling system, is
423 the ACC; more precisely, the supracallosal ACC. If we convert these points into a Talairach and
424 Tournoux space with the *icbm2tal* transform, and we consider Vogt's labelling, we find that it belongs to

425 the most anterior part of aMCC, while if we use the Brett transform, we get a point on the more posterior
426 part of the pACC (Table 5, Figure 4). In both cases, the voxel is on BA 32, on the boundary between
427 aMCC and pACC. The centre of the voxel is the red spot in Figure 2, B.

428 It should be added that, if we assumed a normal distribution for the ratios of the metabolites in the
429 healthy control group, we would have a significant increase of CHO/CR also in R
430 amygdala/hippocampus and a reduction of NAA/CR in pons.

431 In the longitudinal study on cytokines, the only mediator that was higher than normal in two out of the
432 three blood serum samples was IL-4. In one of the three samples, it was not possible to measure it
433 (Table 6).

434 The cognitive evaluation showed a performance at the Stroop Colour-Word Test in the lower level of
435 the normal range (between 21th and 35th percentile); the reaction time in naming the colour in which a
436 circle is printed was lower than normal. A reduced speed at the Symbol Digit test (a task assessing
437 attention, perceptual speed, motor speed, and visual scanning), reduced verbal and visuospatial
438 memory, and reduced verbal fluency were also measured.

439

440 **4 Discussion**

441

442 **4.1 The role of cingulate cortex dysfunction in ME/CFS**

443

444 Several abnormalities have been documented in the cingulate cortex of patients with ME/CFS: reduced
445 glucose metabolism in ACC, MCC, and in PCC (8), increase in the CHO/CR ratio in L ACC/MCC (9),
446 and increased binding of a TSPO radioligand ($^{11}\text{C}(\text{R})\text{PK11195}$) in a ROI covering the whole cingulate
447 cortex (14) (par. 2.3). Increase in the CHO/CR ratio in ACC/MCC is also evident in our patient (par. 3.8,
448 Table 4).

449 These data suggest that a pathological process is targeting this anatomical region in this patient
450 population. Since CHO is considered a marker of neuroinflammation (60), (par. 3.2), and TSPO

451 expression by microglia and astrocytes is substantially increased during inflammatory processes (50),
452 a reasonable conclusion would be that this pathological phenomenon may involve inflammation.
453 These findings match with some indirect proves of cingulate cortex dysfunction, that might represent a
454 consequence of the aforementioned abnormalities. Patients exhibit a greater than normal engagement
455 of the whole cingulate cortex, bilaterally, during cognitive tasks involving attention (Table 2, par. 2.3).
456 Despite this greater employ of brain resources, performances of patients are below normal in several
457 cognitive areas, including task involving specifically the MCC, such as the Stroop Colour-Word Test
458 (30), (par. 2.5). Moreover, among patients with ME/CFS, HRV positively correlates with the performance
459 on the Stroop Colour-Word Test (54), and other cognitive tasks (55). Since HRV has been found to
460 positively correlate to aMCC cortical thickness (56), this positive association might further prove the
461 presence of abnormalities in MCC among patients with ME/CFS (maybe reduced cortical thickness).
462 Reduced resting-state connectivity between aMCC and right insula and the increased one between
463 aMCC and hippocampus/PCC was documented in one study (32). This functional network reshaping
464 around the aMCC might be a consequence of its suboptimal functioning, and it further increases the
465 confidence in the hypothesis that a substantial impairment in this region of the brain is present among
466 ME/CFS patients. An increased FC between aMCC and the hippocampus/PCC has been documented
467 in Alzheimer's disease too (74) and might be related to the memory problem of which patients complain
468 (23), (2).

469 The reduced connectivity between aMCC and the insula has been also reported in frontotemporal
470 dementia, where the lower the L insula resting-state functional connectivity to ACC/MCC is, the more
471 likely is a worsening of cognitive/behavioural symptoms, particularly of apathy (75). Apathy is a disabling
472 symptom that is shared by many other neurological conditions, including Parkinson's disease,
473 Alzheimer's disease, and Huntington's disease. It is defined as reduced motivation, abulia, decreased
474 empathy, and lack of emotional involvement (76). A review of several studies involving different diseases
475 has found that apathy is strongly associated with loss of activity in the MCC and ventral striatum (77).
476 These data confirm the regulatory activity of MCC in goal-oriented behaviour (35). Now, is there a place

477 for apathy in patients with ME/CFS? This symptom has not been investigated in this patient population,
478 to our knowledge, but some authors have implicitly suggested a role for apathy in ME/CFS (78), (79).
479 Several studies found associations between biological parameters of the cingulate cortex and fatigue
480 (par. 2.4). Most notably, the CHO/CR ratio in the ACC/aMCC among females with RA, and the binding
481 of a TSPO radioligand ($[^{11}\text{C}]\text{PBR28}$) in aMCC/pMCC among FM patients, were both found to correlate
482 with fatigue (52), (53). Increase in activation of the left cingulate cortex during cognitive tasks correlates
483 with fatigue in healthy controls, patients with ME/CFS (25), and in healthy subjects after typhoid
484 vaccination (51). These results suggest a potential role of abnormalities in the cingulate cortex in the
485 symptom of fatigue in ME/CFS. Further studies will hopefully elucidate if the MRS study on the whole
486 brain and the Japanese PET study failed to report an association of inflammatory markers in the
487 cingulate cortex and fatigue because of small sample size.

488 Recently, a reduced volume of the right cingulate cortex (BA24 and 32, i.e. ACC/MCC) has been
489 documented among POTS patients (80) and a diagnosis of POTS is highly prevalent among patients
490 with ME/CFS (1), (2). Moreover, as mentioned earlier, sACC is involved in autonomic functions (par.2.2).
491 These data suggest a possible link between pathology in the cingulate cortex and autonomic dysfunction
492 in ME/CFS that should be further investigated.

493 In ME/CFS, the prevalence of self-reported cognitive impairment is greater than the one assessed by
494 objective measures, as reviewed here (30). The lack of sensitivity of the usual neurocognitive batteries
495 in this patient population might be explained by observing that while cognitive tests have been conceived
496 to isolate specific cognitive functions, in the real world most of the tasks require a combination of several
497 elementary cognitive functions. In that context, a delay in processing speed for simple functions might
498 translate into the impossibility to carry on a complex task. With respect to Figure 5, let's consider a net
499 of three cortical units (A, B, C), let's assume that in order to perform a certain task, A has to process the
500 input and it produces, as a result, two outputs, one for B and one for C. B then sends its output to C,
501 that elaborates the final output, which represents the solution to the task. Let $T_{AB} > 0$ be the time needed
502 for the output of A to reach B, and so forth. The other assumption is that, for C to elaborate its output, it

503 needs to receive its two inputs with a delay at most equal to $\Delta T > 0$. in other words, it must be
504 $|T_{AC} - T_{AB} - T_{BC}| \leq \Delta T$, otherwise the task is aborted. Now, if we introduce a delay in processing speed
505 equal to $\tau > 0$ for each cortical unit, we have that the condition for the task to be completed successfully
506 becomes $|T_{AC} + \tau - T_{AB} - T_{BC} - 2\tau| \leq \Delta T$, which can be written $|T_{AC} - T_{AB} - T_{BC} - \tau| \leq \Delta T$. That said, it
507 can be easily shown that for a delay in processing speed $\tau > 2\Delta T$ for each cortical unit, the overall task
508 becomes impossible. MCC is a central hub in the context of higher cognitive functions, highly connected
509 to cortical and subcortical regions. So, it is possible that a slowing in MCC-related functions, as
510 described among ME/CFS patients, may produce substantial impairment in complex cognitive activities,
511 because of the mechanism that we just mentioned.

512 Even though patients with ME/CFS share difficulties in paying attention with subjects affected by
513 attention deficit and hyperactive disorder (ADHD) – a condition characterized by impulsivity,
514 hyperactivity, and pathological lack of attention (81) – it should be observed that the biological bases for
515 these complaints in the two diseases are likely to be different. In fact, while hypoperfusion in cingulate
516 cortex has been documented in ADHD (82), this is not the case in ME/CFS (48), (49), (9), (Table 7).
517 Moreover, while ADHD patients display a lower activation of MCC during the Stroop task compared to
518 controls (83), in ME/CFS the contrary has been reported (par. 2.3). These differences might be the
519 reason why methylphenidate (combined with various supplements) didn't provide relief in fatigue nor in
520 concentration disturbance symptoms, in ME/CFS, according to a double-blind placebo-controlled trial
521 (84), while being beneficial in ADHD (45).

522

523 **4.2 Comparison of the results from our patient with previous studies**

524

525 The only statistically significant alteration in our patient is the CHO/CR ratio for the local spectrum
526 measured in a volume of the cingulate cortex that includes part of pACC and part of aMCC (Table 4).
527 The local spectrum is represented in Figure 3, D, while the voxel and its position can be seen in Figure
528 3, A, B, C. The centre of this voxel is also indicated by the red spot in the sagittal section of a MNI

529 template with respect to an adaptation of the Vogt's labelling system for the cingulate cortex (Figure 2,
530 B). Its position is also marked by the centre of the cross in the two sagittal sections of our patient,
531 registered in the MNI space, with two different labelling systems (Figure 4). This measurement is in
532 agreement with the results of a recent MRS study on whole-brain spectrum acquisition, in which the
533 most statistically significant difference between 17 women with ME/CFS (Fukuda criteria) and 17 healthy
534 women was the increase in the CHO/CR ratio in a ROI defined by the ACC label of the AAL labelling
535 system (9), which includes the whole ACC and part of aMCC of the subdivision by Vogt (see par. 2.1).
536 And assuming CHO/CR as a marker of neuroinflammation (see par. 3.2), this measure in our patient
537 may be also in agreement with the increase in TSPO radioligand binding in a ROI including the whole
538 cingulate cortex, documented in a PET study on 9 ME/CFS patients (14).

539 If we assume less stringent criteria for the statistical analysis by considering significant any measure
540 that is more than 2 standard deviations from the mean, then we have a significant increase of CHO/CR
541 also in R amygdala/hippocampus and a reduction of NAA/CR in pons, in our subject (Table 4). The first
542 result may be in line with the aforementioned PET study, that also reported increased binding of the
543 TSPO radioligand in hippocampus and (although barely statistically significant) in amygdala. But that
544 study also found inflammation in pons, while this is not the case in our patient. Low NAA/CR in pons is
545 a marker of poor neuronal health and, as such, might be in line with some studies pointing to a pathology
546 of the brainstem, collected in par. 4.4.

547 It should be noted though that while in the MRS study on 17 women with ME/CFS the higher CHO/CR
548 ratio in the cingulate cortex among patients is less than 3 standard deviations from the mean of the
549 control group (fig. 2 in (9)), the analogous alteration in our subject is 5.67 standard deviations above the
550 mean of the control group, and it is high enough to be statistically significant on its own. This suggests
551 perhaps that there might be a subgroup of patients with ME/CFS in which the local spectrum acquired
552 in a specific region of the cingulate cortex represents a biological marker. We note also that the MRS
553 study by Mueller et al. involved only female patients, while our patient is a man. This may be relevant
554 since we know that microglia activation following traumatic brain injury is more robust in male mice than

555 in animals of the other gender (85). It is also well known that sickness behaviour manifestations during
556 common influenza are more severe in males than in females, in our species (86), and sickness
557 behaviour is linked to microglial activation (87).

558 Cognitive testing in our patient performed one month before the MRI with spectroscopy revealed a
559 pathologically slow reaction time in a task requiring naming the colour in which a circle is printed. This
560 is in agreement with the slowed reaction time in tasks requiring button-press responses to simple visual
561 stimuli consistently reported in ME/CFS (30). The total score for the Stroop Colour-Word Test was in
562 the lower level of the normal range. In ME/CFS a low reaction time in this task, with normal accuracy,
563 has been consistently documented (30). Unfortunately, separate scores for the reaction time and for
564 accuracy were not provided for our patient, so a complete comparison with ME/CFS studies is not
565 possible in this case. Reduced verbal and visuospatial memory and reduced verbal fluency were also
566 reported in our patient, and despite the fact that memory problems and difficulties in finding words are
567 common complaints among ME/CFS patients (23), (2) there is no objective evidence of these
568 impairments in this patient population (30). So, our patient displays poor cognitive performances in the
569 same domains ME/CFS patients do, but he also shows impairment in other areas. He might belong to
570 a subgroup of patients particularly hit by the disease from a cognitive standpoint. This also might explain
571 the particularly high CHO/CR ratio within the cingulate cortex, if compared with the one found in the
572 MRS study by Mueller and colleagues.

573 The following cytokines were measured in serum three times, twice during the 5 weeks before the MRI,
574 the last time 3 months after: IL-1 α , IL-2, IL-4, IL-5, IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IL-17, TNF α , TGF β 1 (Table 6).
575 IL-4 was the only one to be above normal in two measures out of three (the first and the last). It was not
576 measured in the second sample. Interleukin-4 is a multifunctional cytokine secreted by Th2 cells, $\gamma\delta$ T
577 cells, mast cells, and natural killer cells; it induces Th2 cells while inhibiting Th1 cells, stimulates
578 proliferation of activated B, T, and mast cells, induces switch to IgG1 and IgE, upregulates MHC class
579 II on B cells and macrophages, and it increases macrophages phagocytosis (88); IL-4 is also known to
580 play an important role in the brain: it is a promoter of M2 polarization in microglia (89), a state of

581 activation that has an anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective effect (90). That said, the possibility that
582 peripheral IL-4 might drive microglia activation in our patient is intriguing and should be investigated in
583 further studies. Interleukine-4 was measured neither in the PET study by Nakatomi nor in the MRS study
584 by Mueller et al. In ME/CFS, cytokines have been studied in various sample types, with various
585 techniques, but a recent review concluded that the only consistent finding among studies is the elevation
586 of TGF β (91). A subsequent study on 192 patients confirmed that finding and also reported that 17
587 cytokines (including IL-4) had a level in serum that positively correlates with severity (13).

588 It should be stressed at this point that M1 polarization of microglia in animals is associated to a reduced
589 level of CHO, rather than an increased one (see par. 3.2), while PET studies with TSPO radioligand
590 can't distinguish between M1 and M2 activation of microglia (92). So we might be dealing with the M2
591 type of activation, at least in some ME/CFS patients, and in the subject this study reports on. M1
592 polarization ("classical activation") is characterized by proinflammatory and neurodegenerative
593 functions, while the "alternatively activated" microglia (M2) has mainly neuroprotectant and
594 immunomodulatory properties (90). From a therapeutic point of view, it may be relevant discriminating
595 between these two phenotypes, because while the first one would require anti-inflammatory
596 interventions, the second one should be encouraged.

597 In conclusion, our patient displays a metabolite profile in the cingulate cortex that is compatible with
598 what previously described among ME/CFS patients, while showing cognitive symptoms that include the
599 ones more frequently registered in this patient population. In what follows we propose some possible
600 explanations for the abnormalities found in the cingulate cortex of patients with ME/CFS.

601

602 **4.3 Systemic inflammation**

603

604 A recent review has collected functional neuroimaging studies investigating the interactions between
605 the brain and inflammation in the periphery. Their filtering criteria produced a set of 24 studies involving
606 both fMRI and fludeoxyglucose positron emission tomography (FDG-PET), divided into two categories:

607 *inflammatory manipulation studies* and *inflammatory observational studies*. The former includes works
608 in which inflammation is iatrogenic (induced by typhoid vaccination, for instance); the latter group is
609 made up by works in which results of functional imaging are compared with inflammatory markers in the
610 periphery. The conclusion of this analysis is that peripheral inflammation correlates with activation in
611 limbic and basal ganglia regions, including bilateral hippocampus, the right amygdala, hypothalamus,
612 and bilateral striatum; with activation in midbrain (substantia nigra), pons (pontine tegmentum, locus
613 coeruleus, parabrachial complex) and medulla; it also correlates with activation in the cingulate cortex
614 (pACC and MCC) and other cortical regions (orbitofrontal, temporal, insular, and cerebellar cortices)
615 (93). What drives this increased activation is unknown, but one possible hypothesis is that it reflects
616 inflammation within the brain. In fact, if we consider a 2015 PET study employing a TSPO radioligand
617 ($[^{11}\text{C}]$ PBR28) in 8 healthy subjects after administration of intravenous LPS, we see that the binding was
618 increased in areas that partially overlap with those mentioned earlier, namely: cerebellum, caudate,
619 putamen, thalamus, hippocampus, amygdala, and frontal, parietal, temporal, occipital cortex (87). It
620 should be mentioned that in this study the Authors didn't consider specific ROIs for the cingulate cortex
621 and for the brainstem, and this might account for some of the differences between this set of brain
622 regions and the set provided by the aforementioned review. If we now look at the Japanese PET study
623 on patients with ME/CFS, we find that the signal from the TSPO radioligand is increased in regions
624 partially overlapping with those collected in the two studies we just mentioned: cingulate, thalamus,
625 hippocampus, amygdala, midbrain, and pons (14). Common regions among these three studies are
626 hippocampus and amygdala. Moreover, midbrain, pons, and cingulate cortex are common between the
627 PET study on ME/CFS and the review on inflammation, but ROIs for them were not included in the study
628 on iatrogenic LPS inflammation, so differences might be due to methodological issues.

629 Taking these data together we may speculate that peripheric inflammation drives central inflammation
630 in the cingulate cortex and in other regions, in humans, and that this is exactly what happens in ME/CFS.
631 In this scenario, the increase in CHO/CR ratio in the cingulate cortex documented both in our case study

632 and in an MRS study on 17 women with ME/CFS (9), may be interpreted as central inflammation driven
633 by peripheric inflammation.

634 To further our analysis, we have extracted from the 24 studies collected by Kraynak et al. those that fit
635 the following criteria: fMRI studies in iatrogenic inflammation during cognitive tasks that include one or
636 more ROI for the cingulate cortex. These criteria select three studies: (51), (94), (95). We then compared
637 them with fMRI studies during cognitive tasks among ME/CFS patients (Table 2), looking exclusively at
638 the cingulate cortex. In one study, typhoid vaccination was administered to healthy volunteers (while
639 placebo was administered to a matched control group). Both groups underwent fMRI of the brain while
640 performing the Stroop Colour-Word Test: the typhoid group activated the MCC bilaterally more than the
641 control one, along with the right DLPC (51), (94). Similarly, patients with hepatitis C virus treated with
642 INF- α exhibited increased activation of MCC (bilaterally) in comparison with a control group made up by
643 untreated hepatitis C virus patients while performing a task with conflicting representations (the position
644 of a dot on a two-dimensional space had to be recognized by pressing keys displayed in a row) (95). In
645 both cases, one may infer that iatrogenic inflammation leads to a greater effort in solving cognitive tasks
646 which is demonstrated by greater activation of MCC. The reason why the brain has to use greater
647 resources to accomplish the same task if there is an inflammatory process is unclear, but it is interesting
648 to note that in the typhoid vaccination study, the activation of left ACC during the Stroop task was directly
649 proportional to the level of perceived fatigue and confusion (51), (94). Comparing these results with the
650 fMRI studies on ME/CFS, what we find is that in both iatrogenic inflammation and ME/CFS there is a
651 greater than normal activation of MCC, during cognitive tasks. In ME/CFS this abnormal activation may
652 extend to ACC. The other similarity is that in both cases the accuracy is not affected, even though in
653 ME/CFS there is a slower response rate (Table 2).

654 In this paragraph, we have brought some evidence in favour of the hypothesis that peripheral
655 inflammation leads to central inflammation in ME/CFS and that this immune process is the cause for the
656 abnormalities observed in the cingulate cortex among these patients and also of some of their cognitive
657 symptoms. If that was the case, it would be useful to find an immune marker of the blood that can be

658 used to predict the level of central inflammation in general, and in ME/CFS in particular. Is there such a
659 marker? To answer this question, we have collected some pertinent studies in Table 3. The already
660 mentioned PET study that used i.v. LPS in healthy subjects didn't find any correlation between the serum
661 level of TNF- α , IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IFN- γ and uptake of the TSPO ligand in the ROIs examined (87). Two
662 studies investigating central inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) with whole-brain MRS (52) and
663 [^{11}C]PBR28 PET (96) respectively, found no evidence of abnormal immune processes in the brain in
664 this patient population. But RA is a condition consistently associated with peripheral inflammation, with
665 a high level of blood IL-1, IL-6, and TNF- α (97). Hence, we can consider these studies as further proof
666 of a lack of correlation between peripheral markers of inflammations and signs of neuroinflammation.
667 On the other hand, a PET study on patients with fibromyalgia (FM) found increased uptake of a TSPO
668 radioligand in several brain areas (53), and we know that FM is associated to inflammatory phenomena
669 in the periphery (98). Analogously, a similar study on post-treatment Lyme disease syndrome (PTLDS)
670 – another condition linked to increased peripheric immune markers (99) – found widespread signs of
671 abnormal glial activity (100). Unfortunately, neither the study on FM nor the one on PTLDS looked for
672 correlations between blood cytokines and central immune activity. So far, we have seen that some
673 conditions with peripheric inflammation present also neuroinflammation, but no clear correlation has
674 been reported between the two immune processes; moreover, we can also have inflammation in the
675 periphery without central inflammation, as documented in RA. What about ME/CFS? The only study
676 available for answering this question is the one by Nakatomi et al. where no correlation was found
677 between serum level of TNF- α , IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IFN- γ , MCP1, ESR, CRP and uptake of the TSPO
678 radiotracer in the brain (14). The conclusion is that the only way to assess neuroinflammation seems to
679 be to directly look for it with PET and/or MRS, without relying on blood markers.

680 Peripheric inflammation can trigger neuroinflammation by different mechanisms. Cytokines can be
681 actively transported across the blood-brain barrier (BBB); alternatively, they can passively diffuse
682 through the BBB in regions of increased permeability, such as the circumventricular organs and choroid
683 plexus. Moreover, peripheral inflammation can be sensed by the tenth cranial nerve (the vagus nerve),

684 which in turns induces a response in the medulla oblongata that eventually leads to central immune
685 activation. These mechanisms are reviewed here: (101), (93).

686 As for the origin of the immune activation in the periphery among ME/CFS patients, we note that immune
687 abnormalities have been linked to microbial translocation from the gut into peripheral blood, in patients
688 with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) (102). In ME/CFS, gut flora translocation was documented
689 indirectly by Maes et al., who reported on a higher than normal concentration of IgAs and IgMs to LPS
690 belonging to commensal bacteria of the gut (103). In 2016, a research group found an increase in LPS
691 and soluble CD14 in the blood of ME/CFS patients, adding evidence to the presence of ongoing gut
692 flora translocation in this patient population (104). Moreover, gut microbiota translocation seems
693 abnormally increased particularly after exercise, in patients with ME/CFS (105).

694 Taking all this evidence into account, a model in which immune response to bacteria abnormally
695 translocating from the gut leads to central inflammation, in MECFS, can be considered and tested in
696 further experiments employing MRS and/or PET scans, peripheric inflammation markers measures, and
697 detection of gut bacteria (or molecules belonging to them) in peripheral blood, at the same point in time.

698

699 **4.4 Brainstem dysfunction**

700

701 In ME/CFS, hypoperfusion was initially documented in the brainstem and it differentiated ME/CFS from
702 major depression (106). Subsequent studies failed to reproduce this result (Table 7). But if we look at
703 the methods used for image analysis in these studies, we note that while Costa et al. relied on ROIs
704 manually designed in the scan of each patient, including a ROI for the brainstem, more recent studies
705 performed spatial normalization to a template as preliminary step (107), (48), (49), (108), (9). However,
706 brain normalization performs poorly for the brainstem, unless specific brainstem normalization
707 techniques are used (109). Moreover, AAL, the automatic labelling system in MNI space most widely
708 used for ROIs definition, didn't have any label for the brainstem (36), (110) until the recent release of
709 the latest version, which includes some ROIs for midbrain (ventral tegmental area, substantia nigra,

710 raphe nuclei, red nucleus) and pons (locus coeruleus) (37). In another study, ROIs were defined without
711 previous normalization, but a ROI for the brainstem was not included (111). This means that the lack of
712 replication of hypoperfusion in the brainstem might be due to methodological issues, as it is also
713 discussed here: (101). Analogously, the initial report of hypometabolism in the brainstem from an Italian
714 group that manually designed ROIs on the images from each patient (including one region of interest
715 for the brainstem) (7) was not replicated by a subsequent study that relied on brain normalization for
716 comparison between patients and controls (8) (Table 8). Lack of replication might be due to differences
717 in image analysis approach in this case too.

718 Studies that have specifically looked for abnormalities in this anatomical region have reported inverse
719 correlation between midbrain white matter volume and duration of the illness, direct correlation between
720 brainstem grey matter volume and the difference between systolic and diastolic blood pressure (112),
721 altered correlations between brainstem regions and hemodynamic parameters (113), and abnormalities
722 in brainstem white matter (114). Moreover, abnormal microglia activation has been reported in pons and
723 midbrain of ME/CFS patients, despite the normalization to MNI space (14).

724 There is then some indirect evidence that might point to brainstem dysfunction. Latency delay in wave
725 components of brainstem auditory evoked potentials have been documented among ME/CFS patients
726 (115), (116) and conduction disturbances within the brainstem may be one possible interpretation of this
727 observation (117). Reduced activation of right caudate and right globus pallidus in response to a reward-
728 processing task documented in an fMRI study on 18 ME/CFS patients meeting Fukuda criteria (79) may
729 also point to midbrain dysfunction, given the reliance of basal ganglia on the dopamine produced in the
730 nigrostriatal pathway to function (118).

731 Is there a link between brainstem abnormalities and cingulate cortex dysfunction? Studies on animals
732 have demonstrated the presence of ascending innervation of the brainstem in the cingulate cortex.
733 Namely, monkey studies have shown projections from the ventral tegmental area (VTA) to both ACC
734 and aMCC (119), (120). ACC is also innervated by noradrenergic neurons from locus coeruleus, in
735 rodents (121). In humans, there is some indirect evidence that dysfunction in the brainstem can lead to

736 abnormalities in cingulate cortex in Parkinson's disease (PD), where a loss of subcortical dopaminergic
737 neurons in VTA and neuronal loss in LC are present. In PD, cognitive symptoms related to dysfunction
738 of ACC and MCC are documented since the prodromal stage; moreover reduced thickness, reduced
739 fractional anisotropy, and altered regional blood flow of the whole cingulate cortex have been reported
740 (122). These observations might suggest a model in which the abnormalities in the brainstem reported
741 among ME/CFS patients are the cause of the previously described dysfunctions in the cingulate cortex.

742

743 **4.5 Raphe nuclei dysfunction**

744

745 Recently, tryptophan (Trp) metabolism dysregulation in serotonergic Raphe neurons (and other cell
746 lines) has been proposed as a possible cause for ME/CFS. The Authors started from the hypothesis
747 that the genetic basis for ME/CFS might be one or more common mutations, in order to explain the long
748 list of epidemic episodes, clusters, and outbreaks reported for this condition. They searched for common
749 damaging mutations within the genomes of a set of severely ill patients (OMF END ME/CFS dataset,
750 available at <http://endmecfs.stanford.edu/>), with several filtering criteria. One of the genes emerging
751 from this analysis was IDO2, one of the two enzymes that catalyze the conversion of L-Trp to N-
752 formylkynurenine, in human serotonergic neurons; the other being IDO1. The Authors then numerically
753 integrated the kinetic equations for the following metabolic pathway: L-Trp transport across
754 serotonergic Raphe neurons membrane by LAT1 and its conversion to N-formylkynurenine by IDO1,
755 when IDO2 has no residual activity. They found that this system evolves towards two possible steady
756 states. One of them (steady-state C in the paper) is characterized by negligible N-formylkynurenine
757 production and an abnormally high concentration of L-Trp in the cytosol (123). The two steady-states
758 mentioned above can be represented in a bifurcation diagram with respect to the concentration of
759 extracellular L-tryptophan (Figure 6). This diagram has been plotted by a custom script in Octave,
760 considering the system made up by the transporter LAT1 and the enzyme IDO2, described by the same
761 models used in the aforementioned work, with the same values for the parameters. This code considers

762 $d[T_{cyt}]/dt$ as a function of the concentration of cytosolic L-Trp ($[T_{cyt}]$), and of extracellular L-Trp ($[T_{ECS}]$)
 763 (see Eq. 5, Eq. 6, and Eq. 7).

764

765 Eq. 5
$$\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = \frac{v_M^f \left(1 - \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{[T_{ECS}]K_{eq}}\right) \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} - \frac{k_2 [IDO_1] [T_{cyt}]}{\left(\frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_I^{Trp}} + 1\right) [T_{cyt}] + K_M^{Trp}}}{1 + \frac{[A]}{K_A} + \frac{[T_{ECS}]}{K_M^{T_{ECS}}} + \frac{[T_{cyt}]}{K_M^{T_{cyt}}}}$$

766

767 Eq. 6
$$\begin{aligned} [A] &= 5 \cdot 10^6 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & K_M^{T_{ECS}} &= 2.2 \cdot 10^{10} \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & K_{eq} &= 3.43 \\ K_A &= 4.3 \cdot 10^3 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & K_M^{T_{cyt}} &= 2.0 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} & v_M^f &= 1.2 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{min} \cdot \text{cell}} \end{aligned}$$

768

769 Eq. 7
$$\begin{aligned} k_2 &= 84 \frac{\text{molecules L-Try}}{\text{min} \cdot \text{cell} \cdot \frac{\text{molecules IDO-1}}{\text{cell}}} & [IDO_1] &= 208 \frac{\text{molecules IDO-1}}{\text{cell}} \\ K_M^{Trp} &= 3.4 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules L-Try}}{\text{cell}} & K_I^{Trp} &= 2.5 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules L-Try}}{\text{cell}} \end{aligned}$$

770

771 Our software searches for the locus of points ($[T_{ECS}], [T_{cyt}]$) for which $d[T_{cyt}]/dt = 0$ (steady states).
 772 Then it distinguishes stable steady states from unstable ones, analyzing the sign of $d[T_{cyt}]/dt$ for the
 773 points just next to them. It also searches for the points of bifurcation (124), defined by the following
 774 condition:

775

776 Eq. 8
$$\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} = \frac{\partial \left(\frac{d[T_{cyt}]}{dt} \right)}{\partial [T_{cyt}]} = 0$$

777

778 The two following points of bifurcation are detected:

779

780 Eq. 9
$$\begin{cases} \text{point AB: } [T_{cyt}] = 9.65 \cdot 10^7 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}, [T_{ECS}] = 2.17 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \\ \text{point BC: } [T_{cyt}] = 1.54 \cdot 10^9 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}}, [T_{ECS}] = 9.73 \cdot 10^8 \frac{\text{molecules}}{\text{cell}} \end{cases}$$

781 As you can see, for the concentration of extracellular L-Try set in the study ($1.5 \cdot 10^9$ molecules/cell),
782 two stable steady states are possible, but for $[T_{ECS}] > 2.17 \cdot 10^9$ molecules/cell only the pathological
783 state C is admitted, while for $[T_{ECS}] < 9.73 \cdot 10^8$ molecules/cell only the healthy state A can be reached
784 by the system.

785 Steady-states C (which the Authors propose as the cause of ME/CFS) are characterized by substantial
786 inhibition of IDO1 activity, high L-Trp concentration in the cytosol of midbrain serotonergic neurons
787 and low activity of the kynurenine pathway. Such a metabolic state might have several critical
788 consequences for serotonergic neurons of Raphe nuclei and for other brain regions. In particular,
789 given that in the mammalian brain the cingulate cortex receives innervation from 5-HT neurons located
790 in the dorsal and median raphe nuclei (125), we can speculate that abnormalities in the cingulate cortex
791 may arise because of this pathological steady state, as for instance downregulation of post-synaptic
792 serotonergic receptors.

793

794 **4.6 Altered cell membrane metabolism**

795

796 The local spectrum acquired in pACC/aMCC in our patient shows an increase in CHO/CR ratio without
797 alteration in MI/CR, the other inflammatory marker measured in our experiment (Table 4). This lack of
798 agreement between these two measures lessens the likelihood that the elevation of CHO is due to
799 inflammatory processes. Analogously, in the MRS study by Mueller et al. on 17 female patients with
800 ME/CFS (9), the increase of the CHO/CR ratio in ACC/aMCC is not associated with an increase in the
801 other two inflammatory markers included in their analysis: MI and lactate (9). Since the signal of CHO
802 in the local spectrum comes from choline-containing components of cell membranes, an abnormality of
803 the plasma membrane metabolism may perhaps alter their level, without implying glial activation. In
804 2016, a study analyzed 612 metabolites in plasma in 45 patients with ME/CFS and found, among other
805 results, a significant reduction in components of the cell membranes (sphingolipids, glycosphingolipids,
806 and phospholipids), compared to 39 healthy controls (4). Another metabolomic study found five altered

807 metabolites involved in cell membrane composition (phospholipids) (5). These abnormalities may reflect
 808 a pathology of the plasma membrane that, in turns, might be the cause for the increase in choline
 809 compounds in the cingulate cortex measured by Mueller et al. and by us.

810 A recent study measured the impedance of samples consisting of peripheral blood mononuclear cells
 811 (PBMC) incubated in subjects' own plasma. The measure was performed by an array of thousands of
 812 nanometric sensors. The Authors reported an increase in the real component of the impedance, during
 813 osmotic stress, in 20 ME/CFS patients compared to 20 controls (126). Building an electrical model for
 814 the sample may give some suggestions about the reason for this abnormality. A simplified electrical
 815 model of a cell layer is provided by a parallel of a capacitance due to the dielectric properties of the cell
 816 membrane, and a resistance due to the cell membrane, to the cytoplasm and to the layer between cells
 817 (127). We can add a resistance for the substrate layer between the cells and the electrode and we obtain
 818 the circuit in Figure 7, A. Its equivalent impedance is

819

820 Eq. 10 $\dot{Z}_{tot} = R_{su} + \dot{Z}_{cl} = R_{su} + \frac{R_{cl}}{1+\omega^2 R_{cl}^2 C_{cl}^2} - j \frac{\omega R_{cl}^2 C_{cl}}{1+\omega^2 R_{cl}^2 C_{cl}^2}$

821

822 where $\omega = 2\pi \cdot 15 \cdot 10^3 s^{-1}$ is the angular frequency of the sensors. In order to plot the real part of \dot{Z}_{cl}
 823 and see its behaviour we must find the range of variability for R_{cl} and C_{cl} . Assuming that a PBMC has a
 824 spherical shape with a radius of $r = 5 \mu m$, and considering that the capacitance of biological membranes
 825 is $10^{-6} F/cm^2$ (128), then $C_{cl} = \pi 10^{-12} F$. We have then considered that the imaginary component of the
 826 impedance of yeast cells, measured by this same sensor, is $800 \cdot 10^3 \Omega$ (129). In order for the imaginary
 827 component of \dot{Z}_{tot} to have this same value, it has to be $R_{cl} = 1,9 \cdot 10^6 \Omega$. If we now look at the plot of \dot{Z}_{cl}
 828 (Figure 7, B) we can conclude that a reduction in C_{cl} is one of the possible reasons for the increase in
 829 the real part of the impedance observed in the experiment by Esfandyarpour and colleagues. This
 830 reduction could be due to a change in the size of the cells, but the authors observed the samples in
 831 standard live microscopy imaging and they were not able to record any significant cell size difference in
 832 samples from ME/CFS patients vs samples from healthy controls. The other explanation for the

833 reduction of C_{cl} may be a reduction in the dielectric constant of the plasma membrane which in turns
834 may be a consequence of a change in its composition. In conclusion, if that model is accurate, the
835 increase in the real part of the impedance registered in this experiment could be further proof of
836 pathology of biological membranes in ME/CFS. And this alteration could be a reason for the increase of
837 the CHO/CR ratio observed by Mueller et al. and by us, in the cingulate cortex.

838

839 **5 Limitations**

840

841 We recognize several limitations in the collection and analysis of local spectra. Voxels were applied
842 manually both in the patient and in controls, so there might be differences in the actual anatomical target
843 of each measure. For instance, the centre of the voxel for cingulate cortex might have been placed in
844 aMCC in some controls, and in pACC in others; or in BA24 in some and BA32 in others. Nevertheless,
845 being the voxel volume of 1 cm^3 , it probably contains both aMCC and pACC in most of the healthy
846 controls.

847 Metabolic data were normalized to creatine (to allow for direct comparisons across different studies),
848 with the implicit assumption that the absolute value of creatine of our subject does not differ significantly
849 with respect to controls, in the regions analyzed. Since several studies have pointed to altered energy
850 metabolism in ME/CFS, both systemically (4), (5), (6), and in the brain (7), (8), this postulate seems
851 questionable. In fact, a previous MRS study on 12 patients who met the Oxford criteria showed reduced
852 creatine in pregenual ACC, the right putamen, and the occipital pole, compared to 25 healthy controls
853 (31). Moreover, a recent study on whole-brain MRS showed reduced creatine in the parietal cortex and
854 an increased level in putamen, in 17 female patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda criteria) (9).

855 In order to translate the anatomical image of our patient in MNI space, we only used a linear
856 transformation (Eq. 2), rather than the more accurate non-linear deformation. The linear transformation
857 allowed us to find the MNI coordinates of the centres of the voxels used for local spectra acquisition.

858 But this method clearly affects the accuracy of the results.

859 In the discussion of the electrical properties of PBMCs and plasma, we have used for the sample an
860 electrical model whose accuracy, in this case, is unknown: it has been developed for electrodes with a
861 completely different geometry and size with respect to the one used in the paper by Esfandyarpour et
862 al. Moreover, the range of values that we have assumed for the capacitance and the resistivity of our
863 model is just a guess, based on hypotheses, as explained in par. 4.6.

864 It should also be mentioned that our review of the available literature is not a systematic one.

865

866 **6 Conclusions**

867

868 Magnetic resonance with local spectrum acquisition in the cingulate cortex may be a non-invasive
869 diagnostic tool for a subset of patients with ME/CFS, perhaps including those with the most severe
870 cognitive presentation. Where to exactly place the voxel for spectrum acquisition should be further
871 studied. The region between pACC and aMCC, seems promising, according to our case study and to a
872 previous study. In order to confirm the alteration in the level of choline in this region and clarify its
873 meaning, further studies should combine MRS and PET scans using TSPO radioligands, with
874 acquisitions collected at the same time. Moreover, absolute values of the metabolites, instead of
875 normalized values with respect to creatine, should be considered. Even though there doesn't seem to
876 be a clear correlation between peripheral cytokines and central inflammation, it would be useful to
877 simultaneously measure several immune markers in the blood and search for correlations between them
878 and inflammatory patterns in the brain. Interleukin 4 should be included: it may be involved in M2
879 microglia polarization in some patients, as suggested by our case study. A radiolabeled serotonin
880 precursor may also be employed in PET studies (130), for testing the hypothesis about tryptophan
881 metabolism alteration in the Raphe nuclei. Importantly, studies of brain imaging should also include a
882 separate analysis for the brainstem, in order to overcome the limitations that current methods of brain
883 normalization have in aligning this region.

884

885 **Author contributions**

886

887 Conceptualization: P.M.; Data analysis, coding, tables, and figures: P.M.; Writing of the original draft:
888 P.M.; Editing: P.M. and A.C.; Experimental data acquisition: A.C.

889

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909 **7 Tables**

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911 Table 1: Results for the healthy control groups of the studies collected in Table 2

Study	Methods			Results
	Subjects	Cognitive Task	Brain imaging	Activation of cingulate cortex
(24)	12 healthy controls	Verbal n-back task n: 1, 2, 3	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 40 ms TR 3.0 s	The activation of RL aMCC increases with the difficulty of the task
(26)	26 healthy controls	Color Word Stroop Task	3T MRI BOLDs TE 30 ms TR 0.798 s	The task significantly activates R pACC
(28)	16 healthy females	Visual task: recognition of reflection in rotated letters/hands	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 40 ms TR 2.56 s	Error rate correlates with activation of L aMCC and L pACC
(29)	31 sedentary healthy subjects	Verbal n-back task n: 0, 2	3T MRI BOLDs TE 30 ms TR 2.0 s	2-back > 0-back: activation of RL MCC. Exercise does not change the activation pattern

912

Table 2: Functional brain studies in iatrogenic systemic inflammation and in ME/CFS, during cognitive tasks

Study	Methods			Results		
	Subjects	Cognitive Task	Brain imaging	Accuracy and Reaction time	Activation of cingulate cortex	Correlations
(51), (94)	Typhoid vaccination or placebo in 16 healthy males	Color Word Stroop Task	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 40 ms TR 3.96 s	No differences	Vaccination > placebo: R pMCC Vaccination > placebo & incongruent > congruent: LR aMCC, LR pMCC	Activation in L aMCC and L pACC correlates with increasing fatigue (POMS) in vaccination but not in placebo. IL-6 level (serum) correlates with reaction time after vaccination
(95)	IFN- α therapy in 10 patients with HCV, 11 patients with HCV as control	Task of visuospatial attention with incongruent stimuli	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 40 ms TR 2.0 s	No differences	location > detection: L pMCC was activated in IFN- α but not in placebo IFN- α > placebo & location > detection: L pMCC	Activation in MCC correlates with the number of errors in PTs but not in CTRs
(24)	18 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 12 healthy controls	Verbal n-back task n: 1, 2, 3	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 40 ms TR 3.0 s	No differences	Patients > controls: L pACC, only during 1-back	Activation in L pACC correlates negatively with task difficulty in patients, but not in controls
(25)	9 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 11 healthy controls	3 blocks of mPASAT with associated incongruent stimuli	3T MRI BOLDs TE 30 ms TR 3.0 s	CFS patients were slower and less accurate	Patients > controls: LR pMCC during the second block	Average activity of L MCC/PCC correlates with mental fatigue (VAS) after the task and with baseline fatigue (POMS) in the total sample

(26)	43 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 26 healthy controls	Color Word Stroop Task	3T MRI BOLDs TE 30 ms TR 0.798 s	Patients were slower but with the same accuracy	Patients > controls: LR MCC, LR ACC, LR PCC	None
(27)	9 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda) and a low PASAT score, 7 healthy controls	mPASAT	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 60 ms TR 4.0 s	Error rate was higher in patients	mPASAT > auditory monitoring: L aMCC and R pMCC in patients, but not in controls	None
(27)	19 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda) with a normal PASAT score, 15 healthy controls	mPASAT	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 60 ms TR 4.0 s	No differences	mPASAT > auditory monitoring: LR aMCC and R ACC (perigenual) in patients, but not in controls	None
(28)	19 females with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 16 healthy females	Visual task: recognition of reflection in rotated letters/hands	1.5T MRI BOLDs TE 40 ms TR 2.56 s	Patients showed a higher number of missed responses	Error rate correlates with activation of L dorsal aMCC in both patients and controls, but controls activated more than patients L aMCC/pACC in concomitance with errors	
(29)	38 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 31 sedentary controls	Verbal n-back task n: 0,2	3T MRI BOLDs TE 30 ms TR 2.0 s	Not provided	2-back > 0-back: activation of RL MCC in both patients and controls. Exercise does not change the activation pattern	

PT: patient; CTR: control; POMS: Profile of Moods States; VAS: Visual Analog Scale; HCV: hepatitis C virus; mPASAT: modified Paced Auditory Serial Attention Test; L: left; R: right; STC: Superior Temporal Cortex; DPFC: Dorsal Prefrontal Cortex; IFC: Inferior Frontal Cortex; ACC: anterior cingulate cortex; MCC: midcingulate cortex; BS: Basal Ganglia; BOLDs: blood oxygen level-dependent signal

Table 3: MRS (whole brain) and PET studies of the brain during an inflammatory challenge, and in rheumatoid arthritis, fibromyalgia, post-treatment Lyme disease syndrome, ME/CFS

Study	Methods			Results		
	Subjects	Inflammatory markers	Brain imaging	Inflammatory markers	Brain regions	Correlations
(87)	i.v. LPS in 8 healthy subjects	TNF- α , IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IFN- γ (serum)	PET [^{11}C]PBR28 before and after i.v. LPS 8 ROIs	Significant increase in all but IFN- γ	After i.v. LPS, increased binding (V_T) in all the ROIs: cerebellum, frontal, parietal, temporal, occipital cortex, caudate, putamen, thalamus, hippocampus, amygdala***	No correlations between peripheral inflammatory markers and ligand binding in any of the ROIs or symptoms after i.v. LPS
(52)	18 women with RA, 16 healthy women	-	3T MRS whole brain TE 17.6 ms TR 1.55 s	-	No differences in metabolites between patients and controls in any brain region	Cho/Cr in R MCC (and in other regions) correlates with fatigue (VAS)
(96)	15 patients with RA, 15 healthy controls	TNF- α , IL-6, IL-8, IL-10, IFN- γ , MCP1, ESR, CRP (serum)	PET [^{11}C]PBR28 7 ROIs	Increase in ESR, TNF- α , IL-6, IL-10, IFN- γ in patients	No differences in binding	No correlation between cytokines and binding in any of the ROIs. CRP correlates negatively with binding in the grey matter ROI
(53)	31 patients with FM, 27 healthy controls	-	PET [^{11}C]PBR28	-	In FM, increased uptake (SUVR) in dlPFC, dmPFC, S1/M1, precuneus, PCC, SMA, SPL, aMCC*, pMCC*	Uptake in aMCC*, pMCC* correlates with fatigue (ACR) in FM patients

(100)	12 patients with PTLDS, 19 healthy controls	-	PET [¹¹ C]DPA713 8 ROIs	-	increased binding (V_T) in all the ROIs: cerebellum, hippocampus, occipital, frontal, parietal, temporal, cingulate cortex, thalamus	No correlations between binding in any of the ROIs and symptoms. Each patient reported fatigue and cognitive symptoms
(14)	9 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda and ICC), 10 healthy controls	TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β , IFN- γ (serum)	PET ¹¹ C(R)PK11195	IFN- γ tended to be higher in patients (p 0.07)	ME/CFS pts exhibited increased binding (BP_{ND}) in cingulate, hippocampus, thalamus, midbrain, pons	Binding in the L thalamic intralaminar nucleus, midbrain, and amygdala correlates with cognitive impairment. No correlation with cytokines
(9)	17 patients with ME/CFS women (Fukuda), 17 healthy women	-	3T MRS whole brain TE 17.6 ms TR 1.55 s	-	The most statistically significant result was higher CHO/CR in the L ACC**, in ME/CFS pts	CHO/CR in the L ACC** correlates with anxiety while its value in R OC correlates with depression

LPS: lipopolysaccharide; ROI: region of interest; SUVR: standard uptake values normalized, V_T : distribution volume; BP_{ND} : no displaceable binding potential; dlPFC: dorsolateral prefrontal cortex; dmPFC: dorsomedial prefrontal cortex; S1: primary somatosensory cortex; M1: primary motor cortex; OC: occipital cortex; PCC: posterior cingulate cortex, MCC: midcingulate cortex; SMA: supplementary motor area; VAS: Visual Analog Scale; ACR: American College of Rheumatology self-report survey for the assessment of FM; PTLDS: post-treatment Lyme disease syndrome; *** a ROI for the cingulate cortex was not included; ** this is the ACC of the AAL atlas, it has an overlap with the MCC of Vogt's labelling; * this is the MCC of the AAL atlas, it overlaps posteriorly with the PCC of Vogt's nomenclature, while anteriorly lack some portions of the MCC of Vogt's nomenclature.

Table 4: Local spectra measured by MRS in a ME/CFS patient

Coordinates Brain Region	Metabolite/ Creatine	Patient	Healthy Controls		Patient vs Healthy Controls	<i>p</i>
			Mean	SD		
pregenual ACC/ anterior MCC	NAA/CR	1.3700	1.5500	0.1000	Mean - 1.80 SD	≤ 0.309
	MI/CR	0.4800	0.5000	0.0800	Mean - 0.25 SD	≤ 1.000
	CHO/CR	0.9200	0.6650	0.0450	Mean + 5.67 SD	$\leq \mathbf{0.031}$
Pons	NAA/CR	1.7800	2.1200	0.1600	Mean - 2.12 SD	$\leq 0.221^*$
	MI/CR	0.6800	0.6800	0.0100	Mean	≤ 1.000
	CHO/CR	1.4700	1.5650	0.1550	Mean - 0.61 SD	≤ 1.000
Right hippocampus/ amygdala	NAA/CR	1.4200	1.4750	0.0950	Mean - 0.58 SD	≤ 1.000
	MI/CR	0.7000	0.7100	0.0600	Mean - 0.17 SD	≤ 1.000
	CHO/CR	1.2500	1.0900	0.0800	Mean + 2.00 SD	$\leq 0.250^*$
Right centrum semiovale	NAA/CR	1.7500	1.8000	0.1700	Mean - 0.29 SD	≤ 1.000
	MI/CR	0.4900	0.5500	0.0500	Mean - 1.20 SD	≤ 0.694
	CHO/CR	0.9700	1.0900	0.1400	Mean - 0.86 SD	≤ 1.000

NAA: N acetyl aspartate; MI: Myo-inositol; Cho: Choline; CR: creatine; SD: standard deviation. Values *p* in the column on the right have been calculated using the one-sided Chebyshev's inequality; *: these ratios would reach statistical significance if we assumed a normal distribution for the measures in healthy controls.

Table 5: Coordinates and labelling for the centres of the four voxels of the local spectra

Voxel	MNI coordinates			AAL3	TT coord. (icbm2tal)			Vogt's labelling	TT coord. (mni2tal)			Vogt's labeling
cingulate cortex	3	34	23	ACC supr. (BA 32)	2	28	28	aMCC	3	34	19	pACC
PONS	-1	-25	-29	-	-2	-23	-24	-	-1	-25	-23	-
R hippocampus/ amygdala	32	-1	-16	amygd.	30	-1	-11	-	32	-2	-13	-
R centrum semiovale	27	-12	35	-	26	-16	34	-	27	-10	33	-

ACC supr.: ACC supracallosal; TT: Talairach and Tournoux; MNI: Montreal Neurologic Institute

Table 6: Longitudinal study of cytokines in serum for our patient

Day	IL-1 α	IL-2	IL-4	IL-5	IL-6	IL-8	IL-10	IL-17	TNF α	INF γ	TGF β 1
30 May	=	=	>	NM	=	=	NM	NM	=	>	=
3 Jun	=	=	NM	>	>	=	>	=	=	=	NM
18 Oct	=	>	>	=	=	NM	=	NM	=	NM	=

NM: not measured

Table 7: Studies of cerebral blood flow (CBF) in patients with ME/CFS

Study	Methods			Results
	Subjects	Brain imaging	Image analysis	
(106)	24 patients with ME/CFS (Oxford, Holmes), 24 healthy controls	SPET 99Tcm-HMPAO	ROIs were defined manually in each scan*; cerebellum was taken as reference	Patients had lower perfusion in the following ROIs: brainstem, RL temporal, RL frontal, RL parietal, RL thalamus, RL caudate
(106)	24 patients with ME/CFS (Oxford, Holmes), 40 healthy controls, 20 patients with major depression	SPET 99Tcm-HMPAO	A single ROI manually defined: brainstem; cerebellum was taken as reference	Patients had lower perfusion in the brainstem compared to both normal controls and depressed controls
(111)	32 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 9 healthy controls	CT scan Xenon	ROIs were drawn manually on each scan *, **	Patients had significantly reduced blood flow in LR middle cerebral artery territory compared to controls
(107)	11 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 10 healthy controls	3T MRI ASL TR 2.5 s TE 40 ms	Normalization to Talairach-Tournoux space	Patients had significantly reduced blood flow in the whole brain and in the following ROIs: LR frontal, LR parietal, LR temporal
(48)	17 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda, CCC), 16 healthy controls	3T MRI ASL TR 4.0 s TE 11 ms	Normalization to AAL atlas, several ROIs, including ACC/MCC and PCC**	No differences in CBF between patients and controls at rest nor during PASAT
(49)	17 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 17 healthy controls	3T MRI ASL TR 4.0 s TE 11 ms	Normalization to SPM12 MNI template, several ROIs, including ACC/MCC**	No differences in CBF between patients and controls
(108)	14 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda***), 14 healthy controls	3T MRI ASL TR 4.8 s TE 10.6 ms	Each brain scan was segmented into 5 ROIs **	No differences in CBF between patients and controls in any of the ROIs (cortex, supratentorial WM, thalamus, hippocampi)
(9)	17 patients with ME/CFS women (Fukuda), 17 healthy women	3T MRI ASL TR 2.5 s TE 17.6 ms	Normalization to MNI space, several ROIs (AAL) including ACC, MCC, PCC **	No differences in CBF between patients and controls

ASL: arterial spin labelling; WM: white matter; * Cingulate cortex was not considered as a separate ROI;
** Brainstem was not included as a ROI; *** Cognitive complaints were also required to be included

Table 8: Studies of brain glucose metabolism in patients with ME/CFS

Study	Methods			Results
	Subjects	Brain imaging	Image analysis	
(7)	17 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 6 patients with MD, 6 healthy controls	PET ¹⁸ F ₂ DG	ROIs were designed manually on each study, using TT atlas as reference*	ME/CFS patients showed reduced metabolism in the brainstem with respect to both healthy controls and patients with MD; MFC was also hypometabolic in ME/CFS compared with healthy controls
(8)	26 patients with ME/CFS (Fukuda), 6 healthy controls	PET ¹⁸ F ₂ DG	Normalization to the TT atlas	12 ME/CFS patients showed reduced metabolism in ACC/MCC (BA 24, 32) and in PCC (BA 23, 31); metabolism in pACC correlates with depression (HADS) in patients

TT: Talairach and Tournoux; MD: major depression; MFC: mediodorsal cortex; ¹⁸F₂DG: 18-fluoro-2-deoxy-D-glucose; HADS: hospital anxiety and depression scale; * a ROI for cingulate cortex was not included.

8 Figures

Figure 1. **A.** Photo of the midsagittal view of a human brain. The cingulate cortex is highlighted in orange. The cingulate sulcus (red) and the paracingulate sulcus (green), when present, delimit the rostral and the dorsal limits of the cingulate cortex; the splenial sulcus (blue) defines its caudal limit. **B.** The AAL3 labelling overlaid on the Colin-27 atlas. The anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), the middle cingulate cortex (MCC), and the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) are highlighted in different colours.

A

B

Figure 2. **A**. This picture was obtained by overlaying a template for Brodmann areas on the Colin-27 atlas, using MRICron package. **B**. This is an adaptation of the subdivision by Vogt (Fig. 1.1 in (35)) to MNI space. To draw it, we have overlaid the Brodmann template provided by MRICron to the Colin-27 atlas. We have then transformed the Talairach and Tournoux coordinates of the points *b*, *c* from the original figure by Vogt, to MNI coordinates, using the *tal2icbm* transform, as further reference. sACC is the subgenual ACC (and it includes BA 24, and the subgenual parts of BA 32 and BA 24); pACC is the perigenual ACC (which includes perigenual BA 24 and perigenual BA 32); aMCC is the anterior MCC and pMCC is the posterior MCC (they are made up of the remaining parts of BA 24 and BA 32); dorsal PCC (dPCC) and ventral PCC (vPCC) house BA 23, 29, 30, and 31. The red spot (MNI: 0, 34, 23) is the centre of the voxel placed in the cingulate cortex for local spectrum acquisition, for the case described in this paper. Point *b* has MNI coordinates (0, 30, -8) while point *c* has MNI coordinates (0, 29, 9).

Figure 3. **A, B, C.** The position of the 10x10x10 mm voxel used for the acquisition of the local spectrum in the anterior cingulate cortex, in coronal, sagittal, and axial view, respectively. **D.** The local spectrum for the voxel placed in the cingulate cortex. On the abscissa the chemical shift expressed in ppm, which decreases from right to left; on the ordinate the amplitude of the signal, in arbitrary units. Myoinositol (MI) has its peak at 3.56 ppm; the peak for Choline (CHO) is at 3.22 ppm; at 3.02 ppm we find the peak of Creatine (CR); the highest peak (2.20 ppm) belongs to N-acetyl aspartate (NAA).

Figure 4. **A.** Sagittal section from the MRI of our subject, after co-registration with the Colin-27 atlas. The cross points the centre of the voxel placed in the cingulate cortex (MNI coordinates: 3, 34, 23). The AAL atlas has been overlaid using MRICron. According to this labelling system, the centre of the voxel belongs to the ACC. **B.** In this case, we have superimposed the Brodmann areas to the Colin-27 atlas. The centre of the voxel placed in the cingulate cortex falls into BA 32. See also in Table 5.

Figure 5. A net of three cortical units elaborates the following operations in order to perform a certain task: A processes the input and it produces, as a result, two outputs, one for B and one for C. Unit B then sends its output to C that, in turns, elaborates the final output, which represents the solution of the task. Let $T_{AB} > 0$ be the time needed for the output of A to reach B, and so forth.

Figure 6. Bifurcation diagram for the system LAT1-IDO1 with respect to the concentration of extracellular L-tryptophan. The dotted line represents the locus of unstable states for the system. The solid line in the lower part of the figure is the collection of the healthy steady-states (steady-states A), while the solid line in the upper part represents the locus of all the pathological steady-states (steady-states C). The coordinates of the two points of bifurcation (point AB and point BC) are indicated in Eq. 9. The intersections of the three lines with the vertical one are the three possible states reached by the system for a concentration of extracellular L-Trp of $1.5 \cdot 10^9$. Axes are in logarithmic scale.

Figure 7. **A.** Electrical model for the sample made up of PMBCs and plasma. C_{cl} is the capacitance due to the dielectric properties of the cell membrane, R_{cl} is the resistance of the plasma between cells, R_{su} is the resistance of the layer of plasma between cells and electrode. **B.** The plot of the real part of Z_{cl} in function of C_{cl} and R_{cl} .

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